

Use of modified ZnS in photocatalytic bleaching of eosin Y[†]

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Abstract : The photocatalytic activity of zinc sulphide has been enhanced using potassium chloride on heating at various temperatures. The sample was mixed with KCl in certain molar ratio i.e. 0.25. The progress of the reaction was monitored spectrophotometrically. The effect of various operating parameters like pH, concentrations of dye, amount of semiconductor, light intensity etc. on the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of eosin Y was observed. More efficient ZnS as photocatalyst was found at 673 K for 3.0 h under muffle furnace. A tentative mechanism for the photocatalytic bleaching of the dye has also been proposed.

Keywords : Zinc sulphide, eosin Y, molar ratios, photocatalytic activity.

Introduction

As we step into the twenty first century, we are faced with challenges of purification of water and air sources. One enjoys the comforts and benefits that chemistry has provided us from drugs to dyes, from composite to computer chips; but simultaneously we are faced with the task of treating wastes generated during manufacturing processes and the proper disposal of various products and byproducts. Popular treatment methods for eliminating dyes from the waste water suffer one or other drawbacks. Photocatalytic degradation is found to be a very efficient process for mineralization of organic pollutants where, semiconductor acts as photocatalyst.

Kobayakawa *et al.*¹ reported the enhancement of photocatalytic activity of CdS powder used for hydrogen evolution. For this, aqueous sulphite solution and KCl have been heated. Synthesis of monodispersed spherical particles of ZnS and its photocatalytic activity was observed by Wilhelmy and Matijevic². ZnS has also been used as a photocatalyst for photoreduction of CO₂^{3,4}. Photocatalytic properties of alumina supported ZnS-CdS catalyst was investigated by Kobayashi *et al.*⁵ for photogeneration of hydrogen from water. Reber and Rusek⁶ synthesized an effective CdS photocatalyst by thermal treatment of

the precipitate which was prepared from cadmium acetate and ammonium sulphide in ambient H₂S and reported that photocatalytic activity of CdS powder for hydrogen evolution was increased with decreasing surface area.

The effect of temperature on photoluminescence and electroluminescence properties in aluminium doped self activated ZnS crystal was investigated by Ren *et al.*⁷. A direct evidence for the participation of extrinsic surface site in the enhancement of photocatalytic activity of luminescent ZnS catalyst was reported by Anpo *et al.*⁸. Devi and Krishnaiah⁹ studied the photocatalytic degradation of *p*-aminobenzene and *p*-hydroxybenzene using various heat treated TiO₂ as photocatalyst. Meso-tetraphenylporphyrinatozinc/TiO₂ (ZnTPP/TiO₂) nanocompounds with different molar ratios were synthesized by Li *et al.*¹⁰ by sol gel method at 400 °C. Their photocatalytic activity was influenced by the proportion between ZnTPP/TiO₂.

Kudo and Sekizawa¹¹ synthesized Zn_{0.999}Ni_{0.0001}S photocatalyst (Energy gap = 2.3 eV) by heating at 773 K. They observed activity for H₂ evolution from aqueous solution containing K₂SO₃ and Na₂S as reducing reagents under visible light. The nanosized coupled oxide ZnO/SnO₂ in a molar ratio of 2 : 1 (Z₂S) and 1 : 1 (ZS) were

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

prepared using the co-precipitation method and then their photocatalytic activities was studied by Cun *et al.*¹². Using microwave as the heating method, radial ZnS nanoribbons have been successfully synthesized first time by Liu *et al.*¹³ via a solvothermal procedure in ethyldiamine, combined with thermal treatment in a nitrogen flow. Zhang *et al.*¹⁴ synthesized ZnS nanoribbons over Si and KCl substrate by simple chemical vapour deposition (CVD) method at 450 °C while ZnS nanobelts were synthesized by Changhui *et al.*¹⁵ with pure wurtzite phase by thermal evaporation method. Ashok and Maruthamuthu¹⁶ characterized doped WO₃ photocatalyst by SEM.

Experimental

A standard solution of eosin Y (1.0×10^{-4} M) was prepared by dissolving 0.00691 g of eosin Y 100 mL of doubly distilled water. It was used as stock solution. pH of the dye solution was measured by a digital pH meter (Systronics Model 324). The desired pH of the solution was adjusted by the addition of previously standardized sulphuric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions. Firstly, the calculated amount of KCl was mixed in ZnS and then this mixture was heated in muffle furnace at 673 K temperature for 3 h. This (KCl in ZnS) was used as photocatalyst in the present investigation. This reaction mixture was exposed to 200 W tungsten lamp. The intensity of light was varied by changing the distance between the light source and surface of the semiconductor and it was measured by 'Suryamapi' (CEL Model SM 201). The absorbance of the solution at various time intervals was recorded at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 510$ nm with the help of spectrophotometer (Systronics Model 106). Characterization of the photocatalyst was done by Scanning Electron Microscopy (LEO 1430 VP SEM) equipped with INCA Oxford EDX facility.

Results and discussion

The results of typical run obtained for treated ZnS at 673 K has been shown in Table 1 and graphically represented in Fig. 1. It was observed that absorbance decreases with the time of exposure. A plot of $1 + \log$ (absorbance) versus exposure time was found to be linear and hence this reaction follows pseudo first order kinetics and rate constant was determined by the expression

$$k = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$$

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on the rate of photocatalytic bleach-

Table 1. Effect of exposure time on rate of reaction
Heating temperature = 673 K, molar ratio KCl/ZnS = 0.25
 $1 + \log$ O.D.

Time	Untreated ZnS	Treated ZnS
0.0	0.784	0.784
30.0	0.748	0.739
60.0	0.704	0.686
90.0	0.679	0.621
120.0	0.620	0.568
150.0	0.577	0.520
180.0	0.528	0.456
210.0	0.494	0.415

ing of the dye was investigated in the range 5.0–9.5. The results are reported in Table 2. It was observed that rate of photocatalytic bleaching of eosin Y increases on increasing pH of the reaction medium. An optimum value for the pH was found to be 7.0, 6.5, 7.0, 7.0, 7.0 and 7.5 for heating at 373, 473, 573, 673, 773 and 873 K respectively. On increasing pH above the optimum values, an adverse effect on the rate of reaction was observed.

Effect of eosin Y concentration :

The effect of variation in concentration of dye on the photocatalytic degradation of eosin Y was also studied in the range 0.25×10^{-5} to 1.75×10^{-5} M and results are presented in Table 3. Initially with increase in the concentration of dye, more dye molecules are available for

Table 2. Effect of pH

Eosin Y $\times 10^5$ M	Molar ratio = 0.25, heating time = 3 h					
	0.75	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
ZnS (g)	0.12	0.10	0.14	0.14	0.12	0.12
Light int. (mW cm ⁻²)	70.0	70.0	70.0	70.0	60.0	70.0
Temp.	373 K	473 K	573 K	673 K	773 K	873 K
pH	$k \times 10^5$ (s ⁻¹)					
5.0	3.15	4.16	2.96	3.70	4.30	3.19
5.5	3.60	4.65	3.51	4.64	4.66	3.33
6.0	4.05	5.27	3.73	4.95	4.99	3.84
6.5	4.50	5.89	4.83	5.25	5.66	4.35
7.0	5.63	5.58	6.14	7.42	6.65	5.12
7.5	4.73	5.27	5.48	6.49	6.32	6.40
8.0	4.28	4.96	4.83	5.87	5.99	5.63
8.5	3.38	4.64	4.17	5.57	5.32	4.61
9.0	2.64	4.34	3.95	4.64	4.99	3.84

Fig. 1. A typical run.

excitation and consecutive energy transfer and as a result an increase in the rate was observed. An optimum value for the eosin Y concentrations is found to be $0.50 \times 10^{-5} M$ for all temperatures except 373 K for which it is $0.75 \times 10^{-5} M$. After reaching an optimum value a decrease in the rate with further increase in the concentration of dye was observed. It may be attributed to the fact that dye starts acting as an internal filter for the incident light and it would not permit the desired light intensity to reach and excite large number of semiconductor particles. Thus a corresponding decrease in the rate of photocatalytic degradation of dye was observed.

Effect of amount of semiconductor :

The effect of variation in the amount of semiconductor on the photocatalytic degradation of dye was investi-

Table 3. Effect of eosin Y concentration
Molar ratio = 0.25, heating time = 3 h

pH	7.5	6.5	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.5
ZnS (g)	0.12	0.10	0.14	0.14	0.12	0.12
Light int. (mW cm ⁻²)	70.0	70.0	70.0	70.0	60.0	70.0
Temp.	373 K	473 K	573 K	673 K	773 K	873 K
[Eosin Y] × 10 ⁵ M	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)					
0.25	4.81	5.07	5.50	5.34	6.12	6.04
0.50	5.35	5.89	6.14	7.42	6.65	6.40
0.75	5.63	4.67	5.11	6.53	5.85	5.90
1.00	4.79	3.93	3.60	6.23	5.32	3.28
1.25	4.22	3.45	2.96	5.05	4.52	2.84
1.50	3.94	2.84	2.75	4.75	3.99	2.67
1.75	3.78	2.55	-	4.16	3.46	-

gated in the range 0.06 to 0.18 g and results are summarized in Table 4. As the amount of semiconductor increases, the exposed surface area increases and as a result, the rate of reaction also increases. Optimum value for the amount of ZnS was found to be 0.12, 0.10, 0.14, 0.14, 0.12 and 0.12 g for heating at 373, 473, 573, 673, 773 and 873 K, respectively. But after a certain limit, if the amount of semiconductor is increased further, there will be cause decrease in reaction rate since, any increase in the amount of semiconductor after this particular amount will only increase the thickness of the layer at the bottom of reaction vessel which was completely covered by the semiconductor. This multilayer structure will not permit all the particles of the semiconductor to be exposed to light and as such, the rate of the reaction becomes almost constant.

Table 4. Effect of amount of ZnS

Molar ratio = 0.25, heating time = 3 h						
pH	7.5	6.5	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.5
Eosin Y × 10 ⁵ M	0.75	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Light int. (mW cm ⁻²)	70.0	70.0	70.0	70.0	60.0	70.0
Temp.	373 K	473 K	573 K	673 K	773 K	873 K
ZnS (g)	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)					
0.06	3.82	3.21	4.18	5.34	4.99	4.90
0.08	4.02	4.82	5.40	3.86	5.17	5.33
0.10	4.42	5.89	5.65	4.16	5.91	5.97
0.12	5.63	4.64	5.90	4.45	6.65	6.40
0.14	5.23	4.10	6.14	7.42	6.28	5.76
0.16	4.22	3.92	5.90	6.53	5.91	5.54
0.18	4.02	3.57	4.91	5.05	5.41	5.12

Effect of light intensity :

The effect of light intensity on the photocatalytic degradation of eosin Y was studied in the range 30.0–80.0 mW cm⁻² and results are summarized in Table 5. The rate of photocatalytic bleaching of dye was found to increase on increasing light intensity up to 70.0 mW cm⁻² with all heating temperatures except 773 K for which it was 60.0 mW cm⁻² but on further increasing the intensity, a decrease in the rate was observed. An increase in the light intensity will increase the number of photons striking the semiconductor particles per unit area per unit time. As a result more electron hole pairs are generated, which results in an overall increase in the rate of reac-

Table 5. Effect of light intensity

Molar ratio = 0.25, heating time = 3 h						
pH	7.5	6.5	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.5
Eosin Y × 10 ⁵ M	0.75	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
ZnS (g)	0.12	0.10	0.14	0.14	0.12	0.12
Temp.	373 K	473 K	573 K	673 K	773 K	873 K
Light int. (mW cm ⁻²)	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)					
30.0	3.48	3.10	4.13	2.89	2.98	3.49
40.0	3.75	3.72	4.30	5.36	3.10	4.07
50.0	4.29	4.65	4.50	5.77	5.51	4.65
60.0	4.83	5.27	5.53	6.59	5.96	5.23
70.0	5.63	5.89	6.14	7.42	6.65	6.40
80.0	4.83	5.58	5.32	5.77	6.42	6.20

tion. However, at higher light intensity some thermal reactions may also start and hence, the rate of photobleaching of dye decreases on increasing the intensity further and therefore, higher intensities were avoided.

Effect of heat treatment :

It has been reported that the specific surface area decreases significantly with increasing heating temperature of the KCl-CdS mixture. At lower temperature, the particle growth is not proper and hence the diameter of the particles remains much low (less than 0.5 μm) while at higher temperature, ZnS particles grows up to 1–3 μm in size. A comparative study of effect of temperature is summarized in Table 6. Better efficiency is obtained at 673 K. It seems that specific surface area is not the only factor responsible in deciding photocatalytic activity but the particles size also plays an important role. SEM of different samples have been recorded and represented in Fig. 2. This figure shows that particle size decreases with increase in temperature, which causes higher photocatalytic activity up to 673 K. But on further increasing the temperature, a decrease in the rate was observed. This

Table 6. Effect of heating temperature

Molar ratio (KCl/ZnS) = 0.25, time period of heating = 3 h	
Heating temperature (K)	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)
373	5.89
473	5.63
573	6.14
673	7.42
773	6.65
873	6.40

Fig. 2. SEM of 0.25 molar ratios of KCl/ZnS at different temperatures : (A) pure ZnS, (B) 373 K, (C) 473 K, (D) 573 K, (E) 673 K, (F) 773 K and (G) 873 K.

decrease may be due to the increase in crystal defects at higher temperature. The defects in the crystal provide active sites for the recombination of electron and holes. The less availability of electron-hole pairs may be the cause for decrease in the photocatalytic activity.

The heating time also affects the specific surface area as shown in Table 7. Lowering in heating time accelerates the growth of ZnS particles and thus decreases the specific surface area. As a result, a thick space charge layer is formed, which prevents recombination of electrons with

holes. This in turn, will give higher photocatalytic activity of ZnS in its modified form. In present investigation, the most active ZnS photocatalyst was obtained by heat treatment with a 0.25 molar ratio of KCl at 673 K for 2 h in the furnace and 3 min in microwave.

Mechanism :

Eosin Y absorbs radiations of suitable wavelength and it is excited singlet state to its first excited state, which is converted to its triplet state through intersystem crossing.

Table 7. Effect of heating time in furnace/microwave

Heating temperature = 673 K, molar ratio KCl/ZnS = 0.25,
pH = 7.5

Heating time (h in furnace/min in microwave)	$k \times 10^5 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	
	Furnace	Microwave
1.0	8.70	7.68
2.0	10.24	7.93
3.0	7.42	8.96
4.0	7.16	8.44
5.0	6.40	8.19
6.0	5.63	7.68
7.0	5.63	7.42

The semiconductor zinc sulphide also absorbs light to excite an electron to its conduction band, leaving behind a hole in the valence band. This electron will reduce the dye to its leuco form, which ultimately degrades into products. This was also confirmed that $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals do not act as oxidizing species as the reaction rate remains almost unaffected in the presence of $\bullet\text{OH}$ radical scavenger i.e. isopropanol.

Characterization :

SEM photographs clearly indicates that by adding KCl, it fills empty spaces which exist in pure ZnS form and as a results, the rough surface becomes smooth and more electron and holes are generated by addition of KCl.

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